

The Concept, Importance, and Functions of State Fees

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According to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 113 of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, National Database of Legal Documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan - <https://lex.uz/acts/-3523891>), court expenses consist of state fees and costs related to the conduct of the case. The state fee is defined as a mandatory payment levied for actions that have legal significance or for the issuance of documents by authorized bodies or officials in relation to these actions.

According to S. Berdnikov ("History of the Development of the Institute of Court Expenses," Berdnikov S.S. - <https://izron.ru/articles/problemy-i-perspektivy-razvitiya-sovremennoy-yurisprudentsii-sbornik-nauchnykh-trudov-po-itogam-mezh/sektsiya-11-grazhdanskiy-protsess-arbitrazhnyy-protsess-spetsialnost-12-00-15/istoriya-razvitiya-instituta-sudebnykh-rashodov/>), the institution of court expenses is one of the most important in procedural law. The issue of distributing court expenses is considered at the end of each court hearing.

K. Shmotin ("Ways of Developing the Institute of Court Expenses: A Comparative Legal Analysis," Shmotin Kirill Sergeevich - <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/puti-razvitiya-instituta-sudebnykh-rashodov-sravnitelno-pravovoy-analiz>) argues that the efficiency of the court system is determined by the creation of equal opportunities for everyone to approach the courts and the accessibility of filing claims. The conduct of court cases and the material support of courts require significant expenditures, with large sums allocated annually from the state budget. However, individuals submitting claims to the court to protect their rights are not exempted from paying costs associated with the conduct of the case, except in cases provided by law. The payment of court expenses is a procedural obligation and one of the conditions for exercising the right to a fair trial. The accessibility of a fair trial is an integral part of an equitable court system.

L. Ovanesovnan ("Court Expenses," Lusine Ovanesovna Tasalyan - <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sudebnye-rashody>) argues that a large portion of the implementation of fair justice and the functioning of courts is financed by the state.

The state, as one of its main functions, is interested in ensuring fair justice, but participants in civil transactions whose rights and interests are protected through the court are also stakeholders. This is why, in civil proceedings, the "principle of payment ability" is applied when it comes to paying court expenses.

This author suggests that the collection of court fees is regulated by financial law, meaning it has a complex nature, and that the purpose of imposing court expenses is twofold: 1) compensatory, and 2) preventive or deterrent. The compensatory purpose includes: a) covering part of the state's expenses for maintaining the court system and ensuring its continuous operation; b) reimbursing costs related to specific cases, such as payments for actions taken by individuals assisting the court (experts, witnesses, translators, costs for expert evaluations, enforcement of court decisions, etc.).

The preventive nature of court expenses includes: a) forcing debtors, both individuals and organizations, to pay court costs as a form of regulation (including fulfilling obligations towards creditors voluntarily); b) preventing frivolous lawsuits and evasion of obligations. Therefore, court expenses ultimately fall on the party that has failed to fulfill its obligations on time, filed groundless claims, or made unjustified objections to clearly substantiated demands.

However, it can be argued that there is no procedural procedure in national legislation for imposing court fees on third parties. The imposition of state fees on third parties, whether through financial assets or other forms of non-monetary obligations, implies the involvement of third parties in the case as claimants or defendants. Third parties can only become liable for court expenses if they participate independently with claims.

The method of forming state fees depends on how the state intends to compensate for the expenses incurred by the courts. In countries where court fees are high, the principle applies that the disputing parties should compensate the state for its maximum costs in ensuring the implementation of fair justice. However, except for England and Singapore, there are no countries where state fees fully compensate for the state's judicial expenses.

According to the author's research, in the Russian Federation, the state fees collected cover only 17% or 6/1 of the expenses incurred by the state. The author suggests that an imbalance between the expenses and compensation amounts might restrict access to legal protection through the courts.

State fees cannot be considered as mere payments for accessing the courts.

Since the activity of administering fair justice is financed by state funds, it is carried out not through individual payments, but by the taxes of all citizens. Thus, court expenses cannot be seen as a means to replenish the state budget, and they should not fully cover the costs of running the courts.

A number of European scholars have concluded that, following the example of France and Luxembourg, countries such as Portugal, Italy, and Germany have reformed the institution of court expenses and eliminated them to ensure accessibility to fair justice for all.

In England, court fees cover approximately 80% of expenses. However, in recent times, England has faced criticism for limiting access to courts for a broad section of the population.

The methodology for imposing state fees has been theoretically studied but is not yet included in textbooks or legal literature. Therefore, there is a need to develop and systematize the methodology for imposing court expenses.

Based on the author's research, countries around the world can be divided into four main methodological approaches regarding the collection of court expenses:

The goal of imposing court fees is to encourage alternative dispute resolution and prevent excessive legal action (this model is implemented in Anglo-Saxon legal systems such as the USA, UK, Japan, Denmark, the Netherlands, and Singapore);

The goal is to fully cover the costs incurred by the state for conducting judicial activities (this method is used in England and Singapore);

Striving to find a "golden middle" between ensuring the right of the population to fair justice and maximizing the functionality of court expenses (this approach is used in Romano-Germanic legal systems and countries that were once part of the Soviet Union, including Uzbekistan);

Eliminating court fees to ensure access to fair justice for the broader population (France uses this approach).

The methodology for collecting court expenses can be further systematized by the following criteria:

The timing of payment: 1) before filing the claim (this method is used by countries with both legal systems, including Uzbekistan); 2) after the case has been examined, and a final court decision is issued (this method is used by Belgium and Finland, where court fees are not paid upfront, and cases can be accepted without a state fee).

The calculation of court fees in property-related claims: 1) proportional to the

claim amount (this is the dominant method worldwide and is used by both legal systems, including Uzbekistan); 2) a fixed amount based on the category of the case, regardless of the claim amount (this method is used by Belgium, Sweden, and Azerbaijan).

According to the "2023 State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan," allocated for the first-level budgetary spending, 1,273,817.7 million soums are designated for the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including 1,190,290.0 million soums for current expenses and 83,527.7 million soums for capital expenditures (<https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-6333240>).

The report from the Department of Court Activities under the Supreme Court of Uzbekistan for 2023 indicates that a total of 1 trillion 381 billion soums has been allocated for financing the judicial system, including 1 trillion 289 billion soums from the state budget and 91 billion soums from the reserve fund. This represents an increase of 243 billion soums compared to 2022 (<https://sud.uz/open-info/department-open-info/social-open-info/>).

According to an analysis, 59% of the total expenses incurred by the judicial system are compensated by state fees in economic courts. When considering civil cases, more than 100% of expenses are compensated. These numbers suggest that state fees in economic courts should be reduced.

In conclusion, the amounts of court expenses for both individuals and legal entities should be within the scope of the "payment ability principle," with the calculation and payment procedures being simplified. There should be exemptions or reductions for disadvantaged and socially vulnerable groups. Court expenses are a procedural obligation and an essential condition for individuals to protect their rights through the courts. Therefore, accessibility to fair justice for all is directly influenced by these factors.

As seen in Uzbekistan's economic courts, the procedures for paying court expenses, state fee amounts, and the absence of exemptions for individuals are becoming a "procedural barrier" to individuals protecting their rights through the courts.

In order to theoretically improve the system of collecting state fees and reconsider the methodology of imposing court expenses, the following theoretical proposals are made:

Uzbekistan, based on the results of the 2023 fiscal year, should be included in theoretical literature as a country that compensates a large portion (130%) of judicial

system expenses through state fees.

Furthermore, the author proposes adding a fourth function to the theory of court expenses: providing free access to fair justice for all participants of judicial processes.

These proposals are made based on the best experiences in the world and are aimed at optimizing the methodology for calculating and collecting state fees in Uzbekistan.

A state fee (or court fee) is a mandatory payment levied for carrying out legally significant actions, such as filing and reviewing court claims.

It plays a key role in financing the judicial system and ensures state participation in judicial expenses.

Role of State Fees in the Judicial System:

According to various authors, judicial expenses are an important part of the legal process. They not only cover the costs of conducting judicial cases but also serve to deter improper claims and stimulate the use of alternative dispute resolution methods.

There are two main objectives of levying judicial expenses: compensatory (reimbursement of the costs of maintaining the judicial system) and preventive (preventing unfounded claims being filed in court).

Principle of Payment Ability:

An important aspect in the calculation of judicial expenses is the principle of payment ability, which is oriented around the ability of the parties to pay judicial expenses based on their financial situation.

This principle ensures access to justice for all categories of citizens, including socially vulnerable groups.

Methodology for Levying Judicial Expenses:

Different countries apply different methodologies for levying judicial expenses. For example, in the Anglo-Saxon system, the proportional method is often used, where the fee is based on the amount of the claim.

In several countries, such as France and Germany, a fixed rate is used for various categories of cases.

Uzbekistan follows a combined approach that includes both a proportional calculation based on the amount of the claim and the possibility of exemption from the fee for certain categories of citizens.

Problems and Recommendations:

In Uzbekistan, according to the study, there is an issue with the high state fee rates, which limit access to justice for citizens with low incomes.

There is a need to refine the mechanism for levying judicial expenses, including by creating a more flexible system of discounts and exemptions for low-income citizens.

It is also recommended to develop a more detailed methodology for levying judicial expenses and reconsider the existing fee rates for certain categories of cases.

Main Proposals for Improvement:

1. Reduction of State Fee Rates for Certain Categories of Cases:

For example, for economic cases or cases involving citizens with low incomes, preferential rates could be established, or complete exemption from the fee could be provided.

2. Introduction of Additional Benefits for Socially Vulnerable Groups:

This could include providing exemptions from judicial expenses for pensioners, disabled individuals, and other vulnerable groups.

3. Optimization of the Judicial Expense Calculation Mechanism:

The development and implementation of a more transparent and understandable system for calculating state fees, which would take into account not only the claim amount but also the financial situation of the parties.

4. Encouragement of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) Methods:

Promoting the use of mediation, arbitration, and other alternative methods that can reduce the financial burden on citizens and decrease the number of court cases.

Conclusion:

This study emphasizes the importance of reforming the institution of judicial expenses in Uzbekistan. Improving access to justice by optimizing the amount of judicial expenses and enhancing the methodology for levying them will contribute to the improvement of the legal system in the country and ensure equality before the law for all citizens, regardless of their financial status.